

Affinity partitioning of green lentil lectin in PEG/dextran aqueous two-phase systems

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Lectins are a class of carbohydrate-binding proteins with non-immune origin that are found in various living organisms. Their property of specific recognition and reversible binding to different monosaccharides, oligosaccharides, and glycoconjugates make lectins crucial for many biological processes, as well as invaluable tools in glycan research and related areas. (Cavada et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2009).

The purification of lectins commonly requires multiple steps, leading to the loss in yield; even more, lectins are present in low quantities in raw materials, so, their large-scale recovery and purification are difficult (Nascimento et al., 2010). The aqueous two-phase system (ATPS) is used as an alternative protein purification method, offering mild conditions suitable for biomolecules (Shibata et al., 2019). The formation of two phases by mixing aqueous solutions of two incompatible polymers or one polymer and salt provides an inexpensive, easily scalable, and efficient technique for both protein purification and concentration (Nascimento et al., 2010).

In this study the potential application of ATPS composed of polyethylene glycol (PEG) 4000 and dextran of varying molar masses (40,000, 100,000 and 500,000 Da) was evaluated for the possible affinity separation of green lentil lectin from crude extract. The specific hemagglutination activity partition coefficient and purification factor were calculated on the base of hemagglutination activity and total protein content in ATPS phases and crude extract. Results showed one-sided partition of green lentil lectin to the bottom (dextran-rich) phase in all systems, while purification factor increased with increasing dextran molar mass. Additionally, the influence of different conditions during the extraction step of lectin from lentil was also evaluated.

Key words: lectin, green lentil, aqueous two-phase systems, affinity, purification

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